

IMPROVING THE NUTRITIONAL STATUS OF GRADE 7-8 STUDENTS OF INHS THROUGH SCHOOL-BASED FEEDING PROGRAM

Eleanor Costumbrado Celana

*Technology and Livelihood Education Department, Infanta National High School,
Infanta, Quezon, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10947399>

ABSTRACT

A School- Based Feeding Program (SBFP) was undertaken in Infanta National High School, Province of Quezon involving Grade 7 to 8 students whose nutritional status is severely wasted and wasted. A total of 22 Grades 7 and three Grade 8 severely wasted and wasted students were fed for 120 feeding days during lunch time composed of rice, meat, vegetables, and fruits prepared by the parents' beneficiaries and other teachers. Weight and height measurements were done every 40 days. Findings showed that after the feeding program 23 out of 25, or 92% of the beneficiaries had increased their weights and heights. Two students remained severely wasted. The first one was not able to take her rations regularly since she had not attended the school regularly, while the other one has an insecurity problem and was ashamed of his nutritional status and therefore did not participate in the feeding program regularly. This feeding program was believed to have significantly reduced nutritional problems and can contribute to the student's successful academic achievement at all levels.

Keywords: *nutritional status, severely wasted, wasted, rations, feeding program*

INTRODUCTION

School Feeding Programs in the Philippines were claimed to have increased school participation among food insecure students. In many poor students, hunger has been a barrier to school activities participation. A hunger-stricken student cannot only

comprehend better but cannot perform as well in school activities. Besides, such learners are also likely to quit school because they have to deal with their immediate subsistence needs before they get ready for schooling. Thus, low school performance, low class attendance and high student drop-outs are recurring problems in student's education among poor families.

Infanta National High School (INHS) is one of the public schools in Infanta, Quezon where many students came from low-income families. Food insecurity has been a barrier to students' active participation in school. Most of the parents of the students are engaged in agricultural activity. Unfortunately, they find it difficult to feed the entire family since their own production of food falls short of the demand in the household. Consequently, even children need to engage in some kind of activities to generate livelihood for their households. Thus, many students in food insecure families remain slow in school performance. On the other hand, even if schooling is free of charge, families in such situation still do not have the means to cover some clothes, shoes or transportation. These constraints also keep students from participating in schools but rather force them to stay home and help parents in household chores. Hence, to overcome such problems, investment in education must target not just students, but also family expenditures in a small amount.

In response to these challenges, the Department of Education (DepEd), through the School Health –of Learner Support Services (SHD-BLSS) mandated to implement the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) for School Year (SY) 2016-2017 to address under-nutrition and short term hunger among public school children.

Likewise Department Order (DO) 8, series of 2007 revised guideline on the operation and management of school canteen in public elementary and secondary schools mandate that the 35 % of the net income derived from the operation of the canteen shall be utilized for school feeding program or the undernourished pupils or students. Out of 3,093 students there are 1.13% severely wasted and 5.73% wasted students in INHS during the SY 2016-2017.

In response to the above mentioned problem, School- Based Feeding Program in INHS has been operated within 120 school days wherein the researcher, some parents of the beneficiaries, other teachers voluntarily helped by marketing, preparing and cooking foods feed the students. Feeding is done inside the school compound (School Meals). In the School Meals scheme, students are fed during lunch in school. Such incentive directly targeted wasted and severely wasted students.

School feeding Programs are considered to be a sound investment in education , there is evidence that school feeding programs increase cognition (Kristjansson et al 2016) , educational achievement (Nyakundi, E. M. 2017) particularly if supported by complementary action such as deworming and microfortification or supplementation (Jukes et al 2002).

Food for Education programs successfully enhance the health and nourishment of the targeted children, these are liked by parents, teachers, and leaders. and found that feeding programs helped students do better. McEwan, P. J. (2013).

Many proof-of-concept studies prove that the implementation of the feeding program helps to increase the percentage of enrollment, attendance on a regular basis and decreased dropout rates (Yendaw, E., & Dayour, F. 2015). The nutrition education program has been effective in helping teenagers better understand, feel positively about, and take action on nutrition. Therefore, future programs intended to encourage healthy eating habits among teenagers should include interactive and innovative components. Wang, D. et al (2015).

Malnutrition in the Philippines was caused by a few factors, such as poverty, a lack of access to wholesome food, a shortage of medical treatment, and, in certain places, subpar sanitation and hygiene standards. The issue of malnutrition persisted despite attempts by the government and different organizations to address it through initiatives like enhanced healthcare services, nutrition education, and supplemental feeding. This underscores the need for long-term and all-encompassing interventions to effectively combat malnutrition.

Malnutrition is also a dangerous condition that develops when the body does not get enough nutrients to function properly. Poor nutrition can be caused by a lack of food or an unbalanced diet that is missing or insufficient in one or more nutrients (Chinyoka and Naidu, 2013). Children who do not consume adequate amounts of key nutrients, including calcium, potassium and vitamin C may be unable to work to their full potential at school (Nabarro et al. 2012). Knowing more about what nutritional deficiencies can lead to, in terms of learning, will help families to feed their children adequately to succeed in class. This shows that nutrition is of paramount importance in the academic performance of grade seven children.

For many Filipino families, caring for their precious children is a top priority and responsibility. However, not all are able to meet their kids' needs. Aside from safe play and quality education, children from poor families are often bereft of basic essentials, the most overlooked of which is proper nourishment in their wonder years. Without enough food, these children grow up vulnerable to diseases, hunger and malnourishment, and thus suffer impaired learning abilities in their school-age years, and Throughout adult life, according to studies.

The School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) in the Philippines has been implemented to address issues of malnutrition and hunger among school-aged children. Here are some impacts of the SBFP (1). Improved nutrition: one of the primary goals of the SBFP is to improve the nutritional status of school children. By providing nutritious meals, the program helps ensure that children receive essential vitamins and minerals necessary for their growth and development; (2) increased school attendance: children who are well-fed are more likely to attend school regularly. The provision of meals through the SBFP incentivizes attendance as children know they will receive a meal at school,

reducing absenteeism rates and (3) enhanced academic performance: proper nutrition has been linked to better cognitive function and academic performance. By addressing hunger and malnutrition, the SBFP contributes to improved concentration, memory, and overall academic achievement among participating students.

Conceptual Framework

In the school year 2016-2017, DepEd-funded SBFP in accordance with the General Appropriations Act (GAA) of 2016 under the Republic Act (RA) 10651 mandated to continue the implementation of SBFP in all Public Elementary Schools. Specifically, SBFP aims to address undernutrition and short-term hunger among severely wasted and wasted public school children. The program primarily aims to improve the nutritional status of the student beneficiaries, specifically in terms of their height and weight, by at least 70% at the end of 120 feeding days.

Figure 1. Conceptual paradigm on improving the nutritional status of grades 7-8 Students of INHS

Research Questions

Generally, the purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of school feeding programs on nutritional status of the selected wasted and severely wasted Grades 7 and 8 students conducted for 120 days in Infanta National High School Infanta, Quezon.

Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the nutritional status of grade 7-8 students of INHS before and after the implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program?
2. Is there a significant difference in the nutritional status of grade 7-8 students of INHS before and after the implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program?
3. What are the implications of the findings of this action research for the improvement of nutritional status of Grade 7-8 students of INHS

METHODOLOGY

A total of 25 Grades 7 and 8 students of INHS whose nutritional status were determined to be severely wasted and wasted were selected to participate in the SBFP for 120 days. The school principal, the Department Head of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE), the school nutrition coordinator, and the school canteen manager held a meeting to plan the feeding program that started on September 2016 ended on March 2017 to complete the 120 feeding days. They were also involved in the feeding activities daily monitoring. School heads and other school personnel were oriented on the SBFP mechanics before the program started. Parents of the beneficiaries were oriented on the selection of nutritious food and its appropriate preparation to maintain its nutrients, flavor, color, and aroma. They also committed their service during the program implementation right in the food preparation. All mechanics of SBFP for elementary schools were adapted by INHS in implementing the program except that the budget utilized for it was derived from the 35 % of the net income of the canteen operation. SBFP was therefore limited to the grades 7-8 severely wasted and wasted students due to financial constraints.

Initial weight and height were among the baseline data gathered from the SBFP beneficiaries before the program implementation. After 120 days, their BMI was again measured in order to determine the significant improvement in their nutritional status. Improved nutritional status was indicated by a significant increase in the SBFP beneficiaries' BMI. On the other hand, the SPFP implementation was successful when at least 70% of SBFP beneficiaries' nutritional status had improved (Figure 1).

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the nutritional status of the selected SBFP beneficiaries. Twenty-five Grades 7 and 8 students were selected from among the 3,699 INHS students having problematic nutritional status categorized as severely wasted (88%) and wasted (12%) (Figure 1). They were fed nutritious food for 120 days. (Food and Nutrition Research Institute (FNRI) and World Health Organization (WHO)). The BMI of the SBFP beneficiaries ranged from 11.8 kg to 14.4 kg before the feeding program. The range had improved; became 12.9 to 19.5 kg after 120 feeding days.

Table 1. Nutritional status of SBFP beneficiaries before and after the implementation of the SBFP

Student No.	BMI before (kg)	Nutritional Status before	BMI after (kg)	Nutritional Status after	Difference in BMI after 120 feeding days
1	13.4	Wasted/U	18.5	Normal	5.1
2	13.8	Wasted/U	18.2	Normal	4.4
3	13.3	Severely Wasted/SU	13.7	Severely Wasted/SU	0.4
4	13.4	Wasted/U	19.5	Normal	6.1
5	14.2	Wasted/U	18.6	Normal	4.4
6	13.9	Wasted/U	16.7	Normal	2.8
7	13.3	Severely Wasted/SU	15.9	Normal	2.6
8	14.3	Wasted/U	19.5	Normal	5.2
9	13.9	Wasted/U	16.5	Normal	2.6
10	14.4	Wasted/U	17.2	Normal	2.8
11	13.2	Wasted/U	14.9	Normal	1.7
12	14.2	Wasted/U	14.7	Normal	0.5
13	14.2	Wasted/U	17.5	Normal	3.3
14	13.2	Wasted/U	16.3	Normal	3.1
15	13.8	Wasted/U	17.5	Normal	3.7
16	14.5	Wasted/U	18.3	Normal	3.8
17	14.2	Wasted/U	15.6	Normal	1.4
18	14.4	Wasted/U	17.0	Normal	2.6
19	14.0	Wasted/U	18.5	Normal	4.5
20	14.4	Wasted/U	16.0	Normal	1.6
21	13.6	Wasted/U	17.6	Normal	4
22	11.8	Severely Wasted/SU	12.9	Severely Wasted/SU	1.1
23	14.1	Wasted/U	17.3	Normal	3.2
24	14.3	Wasted/U	15.3	Normal	1
25	14.0	Wasted/U	17.8	Normal	3.8
Mean	13.832		16.860		3.028
Std Deviation	0.594		1.697		1.518
Std. Error	0.119		0.339		0.304

Figure 2. The nutritional status of the SBFP beneficiaries categorized as severely wasted and wasted before the feeding program.

Figure 3. Nutritional status of the 92% SBFP beneficiaries had improved after 120 feeding days.

Table 2. T-test results of the change in BMI before and after 120 feeding days

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Lower	Upper	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Difference in BMI after 120 feeding days (BMI2-BMI1)	3.028	1.518	0.304	2.401	3.655	9.973	24	0.000

DISCUSSION

Findings showed that 92% of the SBFP beneficiaries had successfully improved their nutritional status (Figure 2). T-test results (Table 2) indicate that there was a significant difference in means of BMI before and after the feeding program. It further indicates an improved BMI of the beneficiaries after 120 feeding days. The results translate to a successful SBFP implementation in INHS for the school year 2016-2017.

Conclusions

There were 25 severely wasted and wasted Grades 7 and 8 students of INHS subjected to the SBFP for 120 feeding days. A total of 92% had improved their BMIs after their continuous participation in the feeding program. Only 2 students (18%) remained in a severely wasted status due to their inconsistent participation. The significant increase in BMI after the feeding program translates to a successful program implementation that needs to be sustained every school year.

Recommendations

SBFP must be implemented throughout the year in all schools with similar nutritional conditions to further address rampant nutritional problems in our country. Make some counseling on the importance of nutrition to the body to encourage all severely wasted and wasted students to participate in SBFP to attain 100% result. The government must include the secondary schools to allocate some budget on feeding program to sustain the needed all nutrients to the target beneficiaries.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher conducted this action research on school-based feeding program in a manner that promotes the well-being, dignity, and rights of all participants involved. And the researcher addressed these ethical considerations:

1. Ensured that all participants, including students, parents/guardians, teachers, and school administrators, are fully informed about the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits of the research. Consents were voluntary, and participants were informed that they have the right to withdraw at any time without consequences.
2. Safeguarded the privacy of participants by ensuring that their personal information is kept confidential. Data were anonymized wherever possible to protect participants' identities.

3. Ensured that the research aims to benefit participants and the broader community. Prioritized the well-being of students by providing nutritious meals that meet dietary standards and promoting their health and academic performance.
 4. Secured precautions to minimize any potential harm to participants. Monitored the quality and safety of the food provided and ensured that the program does not inadvertently stigmatize or discriminate against any students.
 5. Ensured that the school-based feeding program is accessible to all eligible students, regardless of socio-economic status, ethnicity, or any other characteristic. Avoided creating favoritism in the distribution of resources.
 6. Recognized and respected cultural, religious, and dietary preferences within the school community. Offered menu options that accommodate diverse dietary needs and preferences and avoided imposing one-size-fits-all solutions.
 7. Maintained transparency throughout the research process by openly communicating with stakeholders about the program's goals, progress, and outcomes. Established mechanisms for feedback and accountability to ensure that the program operates with integrity.
 8. Involved stakeholders, including students, parents/guardians, teachers, and community members, in the design, implementation, and evaluation of the feeding program. Respected their perspectives and incorporated their input to make the program more responsive to local needs and preferences.
 9. Disclosed any potential conflicts of interest, such as financial relationships with food suppliers or vested interests in particular outcomes. Acquired steps to mitigate bias and ensured the integrity of the research findings.
 10. Regularly assessed the effectiveness and impact of the feeding program through ongoing monitoring and evaluation. Used feedback from participants and stakeholders to identify areas for improvement and make necessary adjustments to enhance the program's success.
-

Acknowledgments

The completion of this study would not have been possible without the invaluable assistance and support of numerous individuals. First and foremost, I extend my deepest gratitude to all the participants who generously shared their time and insights, without whom this research would not have been feasible. Their contributions have been instrumental in shaping the outcomes of this study. I am also indebted to Mrs. Emer C. Gestiada, Dr. Ailyn A. Barameda and Dr. Juanito Merle whose guidance and expertise provided invaluable direction throughout the research process. Their insightful feedback and constructive criticism greatly enhanced the quality of this work. Furthermore, I extend my appreciation to Mrs. Amelou M. Mercado for her assistance in developing the research instruments used in this study. Their expertise and dedication ensured the reliability and validity of the data collected. I would also like to express my heartfelt thanks to my family and friends for their unwavering support and encouragement throughout this endeavor.

Their understanding and encouragement have been a constant source of strength and inspiration. Lastly, I am grateful to the anonymous reviewers whose thoughtful comments and suggestions helped improve the clarity and coherence of this manuscript. This study stands as a testament to the collective efforts of all those mentioned above, and I am sincerely thankful for their contributions.

REFERENCES

- Chinyoka, K. (2017). UNPACKING HOW POVERTY AFFECTS THE HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT OF ORPHANS AND VULNERABLE CHILDREN IN ZIMBABWE. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 19(1), 257-271.
- Jukes, M. (2007). Early childhood health, nutrition and education. Background paper for EFA Monitoring Report. *International Journal of Learning & Development* ISSN 2164-4063 2014, Vol. 4, No. 3
- Kristjansson, E. A., Gelli, A., Welch, V., Greenhalgh, T., Liberato, S., Francis, D., & McEwan, P. J. (2013). The impact of Chile's school feeding program on education outcomes. *Economics of Education Review*, 32, 122-139.
- Nabarro, David. "One Health: towards safeguarding the health, food security and economic welfare of communities: preface." *Onderstepoort Journal of Veterinary Research* 79, no. 2 (2012): 1-3.
- Nyakundi, E. M. (2017). Influence Of School Feeding Program On Pupils' Retention In Public Primary Schools In Dagoretti South Sub-County, Nairobi County, Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
- Wang, D., Stewart, D., Chang, C., & Shi, Y. (2015). Effect of a school-based nutrition education program on adolescents' nutrition-related knowledge, attitudes and behavior in rural areas of China. *Environmental health and preventive medicine*, 20, 271-278.
- Yendaw, E., & Dayour, F. (2015). Effect Of The National School Feeding Programme On Pupils' enrolment, Attendance And Retention: A Case Study Of Nyoglo Of The Savelugu-Nantong Municipality, Ghana.
-